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Research Article

**SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERISATION OF COUMARIN
DERIVATIVES AND THEIR ANTI CANCER ACTIVITIES**G.Ajay Kumar*¹, K.Sundeep¹Department Of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Princeton College Of Pharmacy,
Narapally, Ghatkesar, Telangana**Article Received: September 2024 Accepted: September 2024 Published: October 2024****Abstract:**

Coumarins are naturally occurring oxygen heterocyclic compounds having multifarious medicinal properties, hence used as lead compounds for designing new potent analogs. The chromene butenoic acid 3 and the benzochromene butenoic acid 4 which are derived from the reaction of glyoxalic acid with 3-acetylcoumarin and 3-acetylbenzocoumarin, respectively, were reacted with different nitrogen and carbon nucleophiles to give new heterocyclic compounds.

Keywords: functionalized coumarin, antitumor activity, antioxidant activity

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INTRODUCTION:

Cancer is one of the prominent cause of death in the world and based on World Health Organization (WHO) report, more than 13 million cancers death will happen in 2030 [1,2]. It was estimated that one in five people before age 75 will suffer from cancer during their lifetime [3]. Most cancers are recognized by uncontrolled growth of cells without differentiation due to the deregulation of essential enzymes and other proteins controlling cell division and proliferation [4,5]. Although many efforts for treatment of cancer diseases have been carried out and much progress have been eventuated from diagnosis to treatment of cancer, but some of cancer patients do not respond to therapy or recurrence subsequent initial response. Nevertheless, chemotherapy is a basic approach for the treatment of cancer diseases [6]. One of the most important obstacles in chemotherapy is drug resistance to many anticancer agents. Drug-induced toxicities followed by administrating high doses of chemotherapeutic agents to overcome drug resistance were arisen [7,8]. Accordingly, the discovery of new anticancer agent with promising activity and high therapeutic index is an urgent need [9]. Coumarin (1, 2H-chromen-2-one or 2H-1-benzopyran-2-one) nucleus is a bicyclic heterocycle consisting of benzene and 2- pyrone rings (Fig. 1). Coumarins, a part of flavonoid group of plant secondary metabolite, are a wide class of natural and synthetic compounds that showed versatile pharmacological activities including anti-inflammatory [10], antioxidant [11], antinociceptive [12], hepatoprotective [13], antithrombotic [14], antiviral [15], antimicrobial [16,17], antituberculosis [18], anti-carcinogenic [19], antidepressant [20], antihyperlipidemic [21] and anticholinesterase [22] activities. Several natural and synthetic drugs containing coumarin scaffold are clinically well-known agents. For example, hymecromone (4-methylumbelliferone, 2) was used as choleric and antispasmodic agent [23]. Scopoletin (6-methoxy-7-hydroxycoumarin, 3) has been isolated from several plant species and has antioxidant, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory and antifungal properties [24,25]. Carbochromen (4) has beneficial effect in coronary disease [26]. 4-Hydroxycoumarin derivatives acenocoumarol (5), phenprocoumon (6), warfarin (7), difenacoum (8), and brodifacoum (9) are anticoagulant agents that act as vitamin K antagonists [27].

Armillarisin A (10, antibiotic), novobiocin (11, antibiotic), geiparvarin (12, monoamine oxidase inhibitor, antiproliferative), auraptene (13, chemoprotective agent), and ensaculin (14, treatment for dementia) are pharmacologically active agent that

have been marketed and extensively used in clinic [28-31]. Despite numerous effects of coumarins in the search for bioactive compounds, they still remain as one of the most versatile class of compounds for anticancer drug design and discovery. Several studies have investigated the possible use of coumarins in the treatment of cancer cells. The in vitro study of coumarins against renal cell carcinoma showed that coumarin (1) and 7- hydroxycoumarin were potent cytotoxic and cytostatic agents [32]. Furthermore, both compounds showed cytotoxic activity against several human cancer cell lines (gastric carcinoma, colon carcinoma, hepatoma-derived cell line and lymphoblastic cell line) in vitro and in xenograft models [33-37]. The in vitro studies revealed that 6-nitro-7-hydroxycoumarin acts as a selective anti-proliferative agent by activating p38, stress activated protein kinase (SAPK) and p21WAF1/CIP1 cyclin dependent kinase inhibitor [38]. Also, scopoletin (3, 6- methoxy-7-hydroxycoumarin) and esculetin (17, 6,7- dihydroxycoumarin) inhibit proliferation of leukaemic cells by inducing apoptosis [39,40]. The anticoagulant drug warfarin (7) inhibits metastasis of rat mammary carcinoma (Mtn3) without affecting primary tumor growth [41,42].

Objectives:

1. To synthesize new coumarin derivatives based on literature review and purify the synthesized compounds by recrystallization from suitable solvents or column chromatographic techniques.
2. To characterize the synthesized compounds by physical and spectral analysis (IR, ¹H & ¹³C NMR, Mass Spectra).
3. To evaluate the synthesized compounds for their anti-cancer activities.
4. To evaluate SAR based on pharmacological screening.

Synthetic Scheme:

- Infrared spectra are recorded on Perkin Elmer model 283B and nicolel 740 FT-IR

Instruments and values are given in cm-1

- Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectra are recorded on varianGemini-200, varianunity-200 and advance-400MHZ Bruker UX-NMRinstrument. The samples are made in chloroform-d(1:1) or/and DMSO-d6 using tetramethylsilane (MeSi) as the internal standard and are given in the d scale.
- ESI Mass spectra were recorded on a Micro mass Quattro LC using ESI+

software with capillary voltage 3.98 kV and ESI mode positive ion trap detector.

- High-resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were recorded on a QSTAR XL Hybrid MS–MS mass spectrometer.
- Elemental analysis is carried out on VARFIO EL, se Elementor.
- Analytical Thin-layer Chromatography (TLC) is performed on pre coated silica-gel-60 F
- All extracts are extracted with ethyl acetoacetate and water and concentrated at reduced pressure on Buchi-R-3000 rotary evaporated below 50°C.yields reported are isolated yields of materials judged homogenous by TLC and NMR spectroscopy.
- Employing TLC techniques using appropriate solvent system for development monitored all the reasons. Moisture sensitive reactions are carried out by standard syringe-septum techniques.Dry ether, dry toluene is made by distilling them from sodium benzophenone ketyl and dry methanol is prepared by using potassium hydroxide.
- 254(0.5mm) glass plates. Visualisation of the spots on TLC plates is achieved either to iodine vapour or UV light.
- Melting Points were recorded on Melter Fp-51 instrument and were uncorrected.

Experimental Procedure:

All reagents and solvents were purchased from Merck & Co., Inc. (Darmstadt, Germany) and Acros Organics (Thermofisher, Belgium) and used without further purification. Entinostat and vorinostat were purchased from EuroAsia Chemicals®(www.euroasiarnd.com). The progress of all reactions was monitored by thin-layer chromatography with 0.25 mm Silica gel plates (60 GF-254-Merck & Co (Darmstadt, Germany)) and visualized using UV light and iodine vapor. Melting points were measured with an electrothermal melting point apparatus (Stafford, UK) and were uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer Model 1420 spectrometer (KBr disks, Massachusetts, USA).¹H NMR and ¹³CNMR spectra were determined at 300 MHz and 75 MHz, respectively (DMSO-*d*₆, TMS) on a Bruker FT-300 MHz instrument (Karlsruhe, Germany). The chemical shifts (δ) and coupling constants (*J*) are expressed in parts per million and Hertz, respectively. Spin multiples are given as s (singlet), d (doublet), t (triplet), q (quartet), s (sextet), m (multiplet). Mass

spectra were obtained from a 6410 Agilent LC-MS triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (LC-MS, Santa Clara, USA) with an electrospray ionization (ESI) interface. Elemental analyses were performed on a Cos-Tec model EAS 4010 instrument (Cernusco, Italy) and the results are within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values. Cell lines, including HCT116, A2780, MCF7, A549, HL60, PC3 and Huvec purchased from Pasteur Institute Cell Bank of IRAN (Tehran, IRAN).

General procedure for the synthesis of 4-((2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamido) methyl) benzoic acid derivatives (**6a-d**)

the corresponding 2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxylic acids (**3a-d**, 5 mmol) was added to a suspension of 1, 1'-carbonyldimidazole (CDI, 25 mmol) in dry tetrahydrofuran(THF, 10 mL) and the mixture was stirred for 2 h at rt. Then 4-(aminomethyl) benzoic acid (**5**, 25 mmol) and trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 1.2 mL) were added and stirred for additional 10 h at rt. The mixture was evaporated to remove THF and extracted with EtOAc, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. Further purification was done with preparative thin layer chromatography.

4-((2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamido) methyl) benzoic acid (**6a**)

White solid; yield:78%; mp: 261–263 °C; *R*_f = 0.56 (petroleum ether: ethyl acetate = 3:1); IR (KBr): ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3312 (NH), 1709 1602 (CO); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 4.63 (d, 2H, *J* = 6.0 Hz, CH₂), 7.44–7.54 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 7.77 (t, 1H, *J* = 6.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.92 (d, 2H, *J* = 9.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.99 (d, 1H, *J* = 9.0 Hz, Ar-H), 8.90 (s, 1H, CH), 9.23 (t, 1H, *J* = 6.0 Hz, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 43.04, 116.62, 118.94, 119.57, 125.62, 127.78, 129.88, 130.06, 130.75, 134.61, 144.56, 148.08, 154.40, 160.73, 161.96, 167.60; Anal. calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃NO₅: C, 66.87; H, 4.05; N, 4.33; found: C 66.80, H 4.09, N 4.24.

4-((8-methoxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamido) methyl) benzoic acid (**6b**)

White solid; yield: 73%; mp: 238–240 °C; *R*_f = 0.49 (petroleum ether: ethyl acetate = 3:1); IR (KBr): ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3347 (NH), 1712 & 1606 (CO); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.95 (s, 1H, OCH₃), 4.62 (d, 2H, *J* = 6.0 Hz, CH₂), 7.35–7.54 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 7.91 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.1 Hz, Ar-H), 8.85 (s, 1H, CH), 9.24 (t, 1H, *J* = 5.7 Hz, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 43.05, 56.65, 116.53, 119.46, 119.57, 121.62, 125.54, 127.81, 129.36, 137.81, 143.69, 144.56, 146.73, 148.30, 160.44, 161.83, 167.60;

Anal. calcd. for $C_{19}H_{15}NO_6$: C, 64.59; H, 4.28; N, 3.96; found: C 64.66, H 4.20, N 4.05.

4-((8-ethoxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamido)methyl) benzoic acid (**6c**)

Pale yellow solid; yield: 79%; mp: 246–248 °C; $R_f = 0.43$ (petroleum ether: ethyl acetate = 3:1); IR (KBr): ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3335 (NH), 1707 and 1653 (CO); 1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 1.42 (t, 3H, $J = 6.9$ Hz, CH_3), 4.20 (q, 2H, $J = 6.9$ Hz, OCH_2), 4.62 (d, 2H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, CH_2), 7.34 (d, 1H, $J = 7.5$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.42–7.48 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 7.52 (dd, 1H, $J_1 = 7.5$ Hz, $J_2 = 1.2$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.92 (d, 2H, $J = 8.1$ Hz, Ar-H), 8.86 (s, 1H, CH), 9.23 (t, 1H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, NH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 15.04, 43.03, 65.02, 117.43, 119.56, 119.59, 121.62, 125.56, 127.82, 129.89, 137.82, 143.79, 144.63, 145.98, 148.37, 160.53, 161.96, 167.66; Anal. calcd. for $C_{20}H_{17}NO_6$: C, 65.39; H, 4.66; N, 3.81; found: C 65.30, H 4.73, N 3.75.

4-((7-methoxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamido)methyl) benzoic acid (**6d**)

Light brown; yield: 89%; mp: 242–244 °C; $R_f = 0.46$ (petroleum ether: ethyl acetate = 3:1); IR (KBr): ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3346 (NH), 1701, 1659 & 1614 (CO); 1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 3.89 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 4.62 (d, 2H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, CH_2), 7.02 (dd, 1H, $J_1 = 8.7$ Hz, $J_2 = 2.4$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.09 (d, 1H, $J = 2.1$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.45 (d, 2H, $J = 8.1$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.90 (m, 3H, Ar-H), 8.83 (s, 1H, CH), 9.17 (t, 1H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, NH), 12.91 (brs, 1H, OH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 42.98, 56.67, 100.69, 112.54, 114.05, 115.16, 127.77, 129.84, 129.90, 131.99, 144.77, 148.47, 156.64, 161.24, 162.20, 164.90, 167.65; Anal. calcd. for $C_{19}H_{15}NO_6$: C, 64.59; H, 4.28; N, 3.96; found: C 64.48, H 4.34, N 3.89.

N-(4-((2-aminophenyl) carbamoyl) benzyl)-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide (**8a**)

White solid; yield: 90%; mp: 207–209 °C; $R_f = 0.76$ (petroleum ether: ethyl acetate = 3:2); IR (KBr): ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3404 and 3322 (NH and NH_2), 1720, 1653 and 1609 (CO); 1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 4.64 (d, 2H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, CH_2), 4.90 (s, 2H, NH_2 , D_2O exchangeable), 6.62 (t, 1H, $J = 6.6$ Hz, Ar-H), 6.79 (d, 1H, $J = 7.5$ Hz, Ar-H), 6.93 (t, 1H, $J = 7.5$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.18 (d, 1H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.48–7.55 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 7.75 (t, 1H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.98 (m, 2H, Ar-H), 8.90 (s, 1H, CH), 9.22 (t, 1H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, NH, D_2O exchangeable), 9.64 (s, 1H, NH, D_2O exchangeable); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 43.03, 116.63, 116.79, 118.95, 119.58, 123.70, 125.63, 126.93, 127.05, 127.63, 128.36, 129.93, 130.75, 133.75, 134.62, 143.00, 148.05, 154.39, 160.78, 161.91, 165.53; LCMS(ESI, m/z):

$(M+1)^+ 414.0$, $[2M+1]^+ 827.2$; Anal. calcd. for $C_{24}H_{19}N_3O_4$: C, 69.72; H, 4.63; N, 10.16; found: C 69.78, H 4.69, N 10.06.

N-(4-((2-aminophenyl) carbamoyl) benzyl)-8-methoxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide (**8b**)

White solid; yield: 80%; mp: 213–215 °C; $R_f = 0.65$ (petroleum ether: ethyl acetate = 3:2); IR (KBr): ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3402 and 3342 (NH and NH_2), 1701, 1659 and 1601 (CO); 1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 3.95 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 4.58 (d, 2H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, CH_2), 4.95 (s, 2H, NH_2), 6.64 (t, 1H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, Ar-H), 6.79 (d, 1H, $J = 6.6$ Hz, Ar-H), 6.97 (t, 1H, $J = 6.6$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.15 (d, 1H, $J = 6.6$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.30–7.50 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 7.95 (d, 2H, $J = 6.6$ Hz, Ar-H), 8.87 (s, 1H, CH), 9.23 (t, 2H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, NH), 9.66 (s, 1H, NH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 43.04, 56.69, 116.59, 116.80, 119.51, 119.70, 121.66, 123.71, 125.58, 126.93, 127.04, 127.66, 128.36, 133.76, 142.99, 143.41, 143.72, 146.77, 148.27, 160.49, 161.88, 161.93, 165.59; LCMS(ESI, m/z): $[M+1]^+ 444.0$, $(2M+1)^+ 887.3$; Anal. calcd. for $C_{25}H_{21}N_3O_5$: C, 67.71; H, 4.77; N, 9.48; found: C 67.82, H 4.82, N 9.56.

N-(4-((2-aminophenyl) carbamoyl) benzyl)-8-ethoxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide (**8c**)

White solid; yield: 87%; mp: 218–220 °C; $R_f = 0.46$ (petroleum ether: ethyl acetate = 3:2); IR (KBr): ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3400 and 3326 (NH and NH_2), 1720, 1653 and 1613 (CO); 1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 1.43 (t, 3H, $J = 6.9$ Hz, CH_3), 4.23 (q, 2H, $J = 6.9$ Hz, OCH_2), 4.63 (s, 2H, $J = 5.4$ Hz, CH_2), 4.92 (s, 2H, NH_2), 6.61 (t, 1H, $J = 6.9$ Hz, Ar-H), 6.78 (d, 1H, $J = 6.9$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.00 (t, 1H, $J = 6.9$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.17 (d, 1H, $J = 7.2$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.33–7.54 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 7.95 (d, 2H, $J = 8.1$ Hz, Ar-H), 8.87 (s, 1H, CH), 9.24 (t, 1H, $J = 6.0$ Hz, NH), 9.66 (s, 1H, NH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 15.04, 43.01, 65.00, 116.56, 116.74, 117.37, 119.60, 121.61, 123.65, 123.76, 125.58, 126.95, 127.15, 127.65, 128.36, 133.76, 143.00, 143.50, 143.76, 145.98, 148.35, 160.57, 161.90, 165.61; LCMS(ESI, m/z): 458.0 $[M+1]^+$, 915.1 $[2M+1]^+$; Anal. calcd. for $C_{26}H_{23}N_3O_5$: C, 68.41; H, 5.07; N, 9.19; found: C 68.29, H 5.01, N 9.05.

N-(4-((2-aminophenyl) carbamoyl) benzyl)-7-methoxy-2-oxo-2H-chromene-3-carboxamide (**8d**)

Yellow solid; yield: 92%; mp: 212–214 °C; $R_f = 0.53$ (petroleum ether: ethyl acetate = 3:2); IR (KBr): ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) 3402 and 3342 (NH and NH_2), 1701, 1659 and 1601 (CO); 1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 3.91 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 4.62 (d, 2H, $J = 5.4$ Hz, CH_2), 4.94 (brs, 2H, NH_2), 6.61 (t,

^1H , $J = 7.2\text{Hz}$, Ar-H), 6.78 (d, 1H , $J = 7.8\text{Hz}$, Ar-H), 7.00 (t, 1H , $J = 7.2\text{Hz}$, Ar-H), 7.05 (m, 3H , Ar-H), 7.48 (d, 2H , $J = 8.4\text{Hz}$, Ar-H), 7.95 (m, 3H , Ar-H), 8.87 (s, 1H , CH), 9.19 (t, 1H , $J = 5.4\text{Hz}$, NH), 9.66 (s, 1H , NH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 42.85, 56.75, 100.78, 112.62, 114.14, 115.32, 116.59, 116.79, 123.68, 126.95, 127.07, 127.61, 128.36, 132.07, 133.70, 143.12, 143.42, 148.48, 156.70, 161.26, 162.19, 164.94, 165.53; LCMS(ESI, m/z): 444.0 $[\text{M}+1]^+$, 887.3 $[2\text{M}+1]^+$; Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$: C, 67.71; H, 4.77; N, 9.48; found: C 67.86, H 4.63, N 9.59.

Biological Activity

Anticancer activity has been carried out for the synthesized compounds using MDAMB (breast cancer) cell line by MTT Assay. Cell proliferation and viability was determined by 3-[4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2, 5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay [60]. The pale yellow colored tetrazolium salt (MTT) reduces to a dark blue water-insoluble formazan by metabolically active cells and that is measured quantitatively after soluble in DMSO. The absorbance of the soluble formazan is directly proportional to the number of viable cells. Cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^4 cells in 200 μL of medium per well of 96-well plate. The 96-well microtiter plates were incubated for 24 h prior to

Table 5: IC₅₀ (μM) for the synthesized compounds and (STD) on the cells MDAMB (breast cancer) determined by MTT assay:

Compound code	MDAMB (breast cancer)
8a	15.2 ± 0.39
8b	22.39 ± 0.47
8c	9.68 ± 0.78
8d	32.57 ± 0.53
STD	8.45 ± 0.49

STD= Fluorouracil

Data represented as mean \pm standard deviation

Graph 1: Comparison of IC₅₀ (μM) for the synthesized compounds and (STD) on the MDAMB cells

addition of the experimental compounds. Cells were treated with vehicle alone (0.4% DMSO) or compounds (drugs were dissolved in DMSO previously) at different concentrations (1, 10 and 25 μM) of test compounds for 48 hours. The assay was completed with the addition of MTT (5 %, 10 μL) and incubated for 60 min at 37°C. The supernatant was aspirated and plates were air dried and the MTT-formazan crystals dissolved in 100 μL of DMSO. The optical density (O.D.) was measured at 560 nm using TECAN multimode reader. The growth percentage of each treated well of 96 well plate have been calculated based on test wells relative to control wells [61].

The cell growth inhibition was calculated by generating dose response curves as a plot of the percentage of surviving cells versus drug concentration. Anti-proliferative activity of the cancer cells to the test compounds was expressed in terms of IC₅₀ value, which defines as a concentration of compound that produced 50% absorbance reduction relative to control.

RESULTS:

The compounds 8a and 8c showed strong potent activity with IC₅₀ values around 9.68 and 15.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ against MDAMB cell lines where as 8b and 8d were showed poor inhibition activity.

CONCLUSION

Thus the coumarin derivatives 8a and 8c serve as good leads for further studies to develop potent cytotoxic agents.

User Spectra

User Spectra

8d

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